

Indirect Prompt Injection in Browser-Using Agents: A Systematic Analysis from MCP to Host Compromise

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Abstract

Browser-Using Agents (BUAs) are an emerging class of LLM-powered agents that interact with web browsers autonomously, navigating pages, filling forms, and executing multi-step tasks on behalf of users. Because these agents consume untrusted web content and incorporate it into their reasoning context, they are inherently exposed to indirect prompt injection (IPI). This work provides a systematic analysis of IPI severity in BUAs by tracing the threat from its protocol-level enablers to concrete browser-level exploitation. I formalize the Model Context Protocol (MCP) as the technical substrate through which IPI payloads reach the agent, analyze the browser control stack (CDP, Chromium isolation, automation frameworks) to show that no downstream layer offers principled containment against semantic-level compromise, and demonstrate that conventional web security mechanisms provide at best incidental defense. I further systematize MCP-native threats as upstream IPI vectors, survey state-of-the-art defense and attack techniques, and present a formal threat model grounding an end-to-end robustness benchmark of BUAs under realistic adversarial constraints.

ACM Reference Format:

Diego Gobbetti. 2026. Indirect Prompt Injection in Browser-Using Agents: A Systematic Analysis from MCP to Host Compromise. In . ACM, New York, NY, USA, 21 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/nnnnnnn.nnnnnnn>

1 Introduction

For decades, the Web has functioned as a human-operated environment: users searched, navigated, and executed actions themselves, supported by tools such as search engines and interactive interfaces. Decision-making and the execution engine remained fundamentally manual and user-centered. The rise of large language model (LLM)-powered AI agents is now reshaping this interaction model. These agents can plan, reason, and act across websites and digital services, carrying out multi-step tasks over extended horizons, marking the transition toward an Agentic Web [66]. Browser-using agents (BUAs) represent a prominent class within this paradigm: autonomous agents that interact with web browsers in human-like ways. A BUA typically consists of an LLM and a runtime environment backed by the Model Context Protocol (MCP), the de-facto standard for instrumenting agents with external tool and data access. Commercial deployments are rapidly proliferating, with mainstream systems including Gemini Computer Use Preview [37], ChatGPT Atlas [52], Perplexity Comet [55], Anthropic Computer Use [19], and Browser Use [24].

However, the autonomous capabilities that make BUAs useful also render them uniquely vulnerable. Because these agents consume untrusted web content and incorporate it into their reasoning

context, they are exposed to *indirect prompt injection* (IPI) [23]. Unlike traditional web exploits that target browser-level capabilities through code injection, IPI operates at the semantic level: it manipulates the agent's *interpretation* of its task rather than subverting technical access controls. The consequences range from data exfiltration and unauthorized actions performed under the user's authenticated session, to full system escalation via the Chrome DevTools Protocol (CDP).

The severity of IPI in BUAs is amplified by several compounding factors that this work systematically examines. First, the MCP protocol layer, which lacks design primitives oriented to adversarial containment, introduces structural attack vectors through which malicious content reaches the agent's context unfiltered. Second, BUAs use browser control interfaces (principally CDP) that were architected under the assumption that any local controlling process is trusted; once an agent's plan is hijacked by IPI, it leverages these high-privilege primitives on the attacker's behalf. Third, conventional web security mechanisms (CORS, CSP, SOP) were conceived for a threat model in which adversaries operate from the web domain, and therefore provide at best incidental containment against attacks rooted in the local trusted-process domain.

Despite growing awareness of prompt injection risks, a systematic treatment that traces IPI from its protocol-level enablers through the browser control stack to concrete exploitation and benchmarked defenses remains lacking. Existing studies either focus narrowly on LLM-level jailbreaking, catalog MCP threats without connecting them to downstream browser-level impact, or evaluate defenses in isolation from realistic agentic browsing deployments.

This work addresses the gap with the following contributions:

- (1) A structured analysis of MCP as the technical foundational layer of BUAs, formalizing its architectural properties as vectors that enable and amplify indirect prompt injection.
- (2) A comparative analysis of traditional and agentic web browsing failure modes, demonstrating that conventional web security mechanisms do not principally defend against IPI-class threats originating from the local trusted-process domain.
- (3) A systematization of MCP-native threats, classified by system plane and lifecycle phase, with explicit mapping to their role as upstream enablers of indirect prompt injection.
- (4) A survey of state-of-the-art defense and attack techniques for IPI in agentic systems, covering model-level, application-level, and architectural approaches.
- (5) A formal threat model grounding a BUAs IPI robustness benchmark, with few mainstream LLMs and under realistic adversarial constraints.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 1.1 introduces MCP and its security-relevant primitives. Section 2 describes the architectural models through which agents control

browsers, the trust assumptions they rely on, and the Chromium security boundaries they operate across. Section 3 compares traditional and agentic web browsing failure modes, highlighting why established defenses fall short against semantic-level attacks. Section 4 systematizes MCP-native threats as upstream vectors to IPI. Section 5 provides an in-depth treatment of indirect prompt injection in agentic systems, covering both defense and attack techniques. Section 6 formalizes the threat model, Section 7 illustrates the benchmark, and finally Section 8 provides empirical evidence to the thesis and proposals for future work.

1.1 Model Context Protocol

MCP governs how external content enters the agent's reasoning context, therefore understanding MCP is essential to analyse concretely indirect prompt injection in BUAs. Defined by Anthropic to standardize how AI applications integrate with external environments and tools, with the first official specification in November 2024, MCP is now de-facto the technical framework of modern LLM-powered agentic systems.

The literature models MCP as a client-server application communication layer for the instrumentation of AI agentic systems with external world interaction capabilities, where:

- the **Host** is the AI application embedding the model
- the **Client** mediates communication
- the **Server** exposes capabilities via structured descriptors

In a nutshell it standardises three operational aspects:

- Capability registration procedure
- Capabilities usage semantics
- Model perception method of the environment

1.1.1 Core Technical Primitives. MCP relies on:

- **JSON-RPC 2.0:** provides the semantics of the interaction. MCP has a stateless execution model, strict schema-based method parameters and a deterministic request-response correlation via identifiers
- **HTTP Streamable:** MCP employs a long-lived bidirectional HTTP connection, as such, the server can notify capability updates anytime throughout the session, enabling runtime mutation of tool metadata. Alternatively, the protocol specification defines also STDIO as communication protocol, for local settings.

1.1.2 Capability Registration. Upon initialization, the MCP Server registers all primitive capabilities. This registration step constitutes a semantic exposure of affordances[34] to the LLM. Critically, as demonstrated empirically, tool descriptions are ingested verbatim into model context, making this phase security-critical. From an indirect prompt injection perspective, any content that enters the model context without semantic validation constitutes a potential injection surface; capability registration is the first such surface in the MCP lifecycle.

1.1.3 Primitive MCP Server Capabilities. MCP denotes three kinds of primitive capabilities, the MCP server exposes:

- **Tools:** Tools describe actionable primitive capabilities and are exposed by the MCP server to the MCP client through the JSON-RPC 2.0 API specification. Security analyses show

that tool descriptions constitute a primary attack surface (e.g., tool poisoning, shadowing, coordination attacks) [38].

- **Resources:** Structured or serialised data that provides additional context to the model. Resources allow servers to share data that provides context to language models, such as files, database schemas, or application-specific information. Each resource is uniquely identified by a URI. Conceptually, resources are read-only contextual augmentations.
- **Prompts:** Pre-defined templates or instructions that guide language model interactions. Prompts function as reusable reasoning scaffolds,

Collectively, these primitives define the interface through which external content reaches the LLM. Because MCP was designed primarily for capability exposure and interoperability rather than adversarial containment, none of these primitives enforce semantic validation of the data they transport. This architectural property has direct implications for indirect prompt injection: malicious instructions embedded in tool outputs, resource payloads, or prompt templates are delivered to the agent's context with the same implicit trust as legitimate content. The following sections examine the browser control infrastructure atop which MCP operates, progressively building toward the threat model.

2 Agentic Browser Control System Models

Having established MCP as the protocol layer through which external content enters the agent, this section examines the downstream infrastructure that determines what an agent can *do* once its plan has been influenced. The severity of indirect prompt injection is fundamentally determined by the capabilities available to a compromised agent; understanding these control models is therefore prerequisite to assessing IPI impact.

The state-of-the-art of systems instrumenting agents with browser control capabilities depicts two canonical control models, according to the core component implementing browsing policy enforcement and trust verification.

Browser-centric control model. Composed of:

- **Browser extension:** implements the core domain logic and interacts with the browser through the extensions API.
- **MCP Bridge:** middleware between the MCP client and the extension.

Due to the browser security architecture, extensions cannot open arbitrary TCP sockets, bind to local ports, or communicate directly through OS-level transports with external processes. MCP, however, requires either HTTP streamable or stdio transport. The bridge therefore translates MCP-specific transports into browser-compatible messaging primitives (e.g., stdio or WebSockets).

Concretely, the mechanism relies on declaring a whitelisted system binary (native host) in the extension's `manifest.json`. This binary is started by the browser as a child process; the browser then allows the extension to communicate with it (via stdio, WebSockets, or HTTP), thereby crossing the browser trust boundary.

Server-centric control model. The core domain resides in a separate MCP server, which communicates directly with the browser engine executed in debugging mode via the Chrome DevTools

Protocol (CDP). This protocol exposes powerful automation capabilities, effectively allowing the MCP server to control the entire browser lifecycle. Consequently, system trust is rooted in the MCP server. Moreover, more widespread solutions introduce a browser automation layer (e.g., Playwright) acting as a proxy to CDP.

Current commercial solutions exhibit both architectural flavours, with a clear trend toward adoption of the server-rooted control model (or hybrids derived from it). Accordingly, the analysis in the following chapters and the benchmark design primarily target this model.

2.1 Capabilities Interface - Chrome DevTools Protocol (CDP)

The practical impact of an indirect prompt injection attack on a BUA is bounded by the set of browser primitives the agent can invoke. CDP defines this set, and understanding its scope is essential to quantifying IPI blast radius.

Chromium constitutes a foundational open-source component of the contemporary Web ecosystem, serving as the engine of major commercial browsers such as Chrome, Brave, and Opera. Chromium exposes a structured control interface known as the Chrome DevTools Protocol (CDP) [36], originally designed to enable debugging, inspection, profiling, and instrumentation of the browser engine.

The CDP API is organized into a collection of domains (e.g., DOM, Debugger, Network, Runtime), each defining a set of commands and corresponding events. Commands and events are serialized as schema-defined JSON objects and exchanged over a WebSocket transport.

When a Chromium-based browser executing in debugging mode, exposes a WebSocket endpoint bound to a local interface. Any local process capable of connecting to this endpoint can issue CDP commands and receive events. This mechanism effectively transforms the browser into a remotely instrumentable execution environment controlled by a separate local process.

From a security perspective, CDP is not merely a debugging utility but a capability amplification interface. While execution ultimately occurs within sandboxed renderer processes, CDP grants external processes high-privilege control primitives that bypass traditional web-domain trust boundaries.

For the scope of this work, the following CDP domains are of particular relevance due to their direct impact on browsing integrity and trust enforcement:

- **Runtime** (e.g., `Runtime.evaluate`, `Runtime.runScript`): This domain exposes the JavaScript execution environment of a target page. It allows remote evaluation of arbitrary JavaScript code within the page's execution context and provides access to mirror objects representing in-memory state. Arbitrary code execution within active browsing contexts. This capability enables direct alteration of application state, extraction of secrets from JavaScript memory, modification of authentication flows, and pivoting into deeper front-end logic manipulation.

- **Debugger** (e.g., `Debugger.evaluateOnCallFrame`): Exposes full debugging primitives over JavaScript execution. It permits breakpoint management, call stack inspection, and step-wise control of script execution, and is extensively used in automated end-to-end testing frameworks.

Control over execution flow, including the ability to pause execution in privileged contexts, modify runtime state, or alter control paths before security checks are completed.

- **DOM** (e.g., `DOM.setNodeValue`, `DOM.setAttributeValue`): Provides fine-grained read/write access to the Document Object Model, allowing structural and content-level modification of rendered documents.

Although seemingly confined to UI manipulation, DOM-level modifications through CDP can inject scripts, create phishing overlays, rewrite application logic, or alter security-relevant attributes. Crucially, these operations originate from a privileged local process and therefore bypass the content-script sandbox and traditional same-origin enforcement mechanisms.

Collectively, these domains expose primitives that, when controlled by an external local process, collapse the conventional browser trust model. While CDP was designed for developer instrumentation, its capability surface enables arbitrary read/write access across browsing targets, fundamentally shifting the trust assumptions upon which web security mechanisms are built. In the context of indirect prompt injection, these are the concrete primitives an IPI-compromised agent can invoke: the ability to execute arbitrary JavaScript, modify DOM state, and access sensitive artifacts translates a semantic-level attack into full browser-level exploitation.

2.2 Trust Model

The trust architecture of a BUA determines which assumptions an indirect prompt injection must violate and which components absorb the resulting failure. This subsection formalizes these trust relationships.

Trust can be understood as the decision to rely on a system component to behave within assumed guardrails, with the explicit awareness that deviations beyond those guardrails may cause harm. Residual risk arises precisely from the possibility that such deviations occur despite existing constraints.

In the context of agentic web browsing automation, trust refers to the degree to which individual system domains are relied upon to execute a user's browsing request in a manner that:

- remains consistent with the intended objective, and
- does not introduce harmful or unintended side effects.

Under the server-centric control model considered here, the system is reduced to:

- a browser instance executing in debugging mode,
- controlled end-to-end via CDP by an external process,
- and an MCP server implementing authentication and authorization mechanisms over its exposed capabilities.

The browser constitutes the system's trust root. It is the ultimate execution domain of web interaction operations, cannot be externally verified by other components, and intentionally exposes its control interface via CDP.

However, the power of CDP capabilities fundamentally alters traditional browser trust boundaries. By design, the browser assumes that any local process connecting to the debugging interface is trustworthy. Consequently, it delegates policy enforcement and trust verification authority to that process. This effectively extends the Trusted Computing Base (TCB) beyond the browser itself.

This trust architecture is grounded in a weak but implicit assumption: that any local process is user-owned and therefore authorized. Under this model, harmful browsing behavior originating from a local process is presumed to stem from an earlier system-wide compromise that already violated foundational trust assumptions.

Trust Boundary Fragility. The trust boundary between the TCB and clients consuming exposed browsing capabilities is therefore critical. Compromise of the MCP server's access control mechanisms may have cascading effects on the entire automation stack.

Moreover, due to the non-deterministic nature of LLM-based agents, this trust boundary lacks intrinsic robustness. Failure modes such as indirect prompt injection cannot be reliably detected or contained by the MCP server. While the server can enforce capability-level constraints, it is structurally incapable of verifying semantic alignment with the original user intent. User intent is not machine-verifiable.

Blast Radius Containment. Given the structural impossibility of complete semantic verification, the automation layer must prioritize containment. Robust browsing policies can mitigate impact by:

- Restricting exposed CDP domains to a minimal subset required for task completion (principle of least privilege).
- Sandboxing JavaScript execution within isolated contexts.
- Enforcing strict separation between read-only and state-mutating capabilities.

Such measures do not prevent alignment failures but reduce their blast radius, aligning with defense-in-depth principles for agentic systems. In this trust model, security emerges not from perfect intent verification, but from layered containment, constrained capability exposure, and explicit acknowledgment of residual risk.

2.3 Chromium Security Architecture

A natural question when assessing IPI severity is whether the browser's own security mechanisms contain the damage. This section outlines the security architecture of Chromium [21], focusing on the runtime security properties it aims to enforce, the design principles underlying these guarantees, and the reasons why such guarantees do not constrain browser control via the Chrome DevTools Protocol (CDP).

Execution Domain Separation. At runtime, Chromium adopts an architecture that besides isolating distinct processes, separates their execution into two primary domains:

- **Browser Process (Browser Kernel):** This component models the user. It manages global application state, coordinates windows and tabs, and mediates privileged interactions with

the operating system, including disk access, network operations, and UI rendering.

- **Renderer Processes (Rendering Engine):** These components model the web. Each renderer processes untrusted web content, including HTML parsing, JavaScript execution, layout computation, and image decoding.

Throughout Chromium's security design process, the renderer has been treated under a *loose trust assumption*: it is considered potentially compromised by design. Since it executes adversary-controlled web content, it is modeled as an attacker-controlled domain. In contrast, the kernel process constitutes the Trusted Computing Base (TCB), enforcing security invariants and mediating all privileged operations.

Security as Structural Constraint. Chromium security is not implemented solely as runtime checks layered atop functionality; rather, it is embedded as a structural property of the architecture. The multi-process design reflects core security principles:

- **Defense-in-depth**, via multiple orthogonal isolation layers.
- **Strict least privilege**, minimizing renderer capabilities.
- **Zero-trust posture toward the renderer**, assuming compromise as a baseline condition.

Importantly, many mechanisms are reactive and containment-oriented rather than purely preventive. While blocking interaction with privileged system and network APIs, Remote code execution (RCE) within a renderer is treated as an eventual possibility. The architecture is therefore optimized to limit post-compromise capabilities rather than to eliminate exploitability at its root.

Primary Security Mechanisms. Renderer processes are constrained through three principal mechanisms:

- **Process Sandboxing:** Each renderer executes within a constrained operating system sandbox. Direct access to filesystem, raw network sockets, device interfaces, and other privileged OS APIs is denied. Only a minimal set of system calls necessary for rendering is permitted.
- **Site Isolation and Context Isolation:** Renderer processes are restricted to a single site instance and can access only data relevant to that origin. Web security invariants are enforced in coordination with browser-mediated Inter-Process Communication (IPC). IPC messages are authenticated and validated by the browser process before privileged actions are executed.
- **Input/Output Mediation:** Renderers do not directly interact with network stacks or UI subsystems. Network requests are brokered by the browser process, and rendered output is transmitted as validated bitmaps to the display subsystem. This mediation prevents compromised renderers from directly invoking privileged UI or network operations.

Collectively, these mechanisms ensure that exploitation of web content results in a confined, ephemeral failure within the compromised renderer, rather than full system compromise.

Non-Applicability to CDP-Based Control. These execution guardrails are explicitly oriented toward threats originating from the *web domain*. They assume that adversarial influence arises from remote web content executed within renderer processes.

In contrast, the Chrome DevTools Protocol (CDP) exposes a privileged control interface intended for debugging and automation. CDP operates via a local transport channel (typically a WebSocket endpoint bound to localhost). Although CDP commands are ultimately executed within sandboxed renderer processes, the authority to issue such commands originates outside the web threat model. The Chromium security architecture does not treat the local CDP client as adversarial. Instead, it assumes that local processes are trusted and user-authorized.

From a formal security perspective, CDP constitutes a privileged control plane external to the renderer isolation model. It effectively extends the TCB to any local process capable of connecting to the debugging endpoint. Consequently, while the architecture robustly contains web-originated attacks, it intentionally does not constrain local automation or debugging clients. This design choice reflects an environmental trust assumption rather than an oversight.

Moreover, certain CDP domains invoke browser internal functionalities. If misused by an unauthorized local actor, these calls may bypass assumptions about renderer confinement and directly leverage TCB functionality.

Renderer Evasion Through Loopback Scenario. A notable edge case arises when a compromised renderer attempts to access the loopback interface and communicate with the CDP WebSocket endpoint. In such a scenario, untrusted web content could theoretically attempt to bridge into the debugging control plane and escape its isolation boundary.

Mitigations reduce, but do not categorically eliminate, this risk:

- Web-native protections such as CORS restrict cross-origin requests.
- Chromium-level validations (e.g., DevToolsAgentHost checks and Host header validation) constrain unauthorized DevTools access.
- Emerging browser-wide mitigations inspired by the *Private Network Access* (PNA) specification extend CORS-like protections to requests targeting local and private network resources.

The PNA model addresses a long-standing ambiguity in handling web-initiated requests to loopback or internal networks by introducing explicit permission and preflight requirements. Modern Chromium-based browsers partially implement these controls, thereby strengthening isolation between web content and local debugging endpoints.

Security Implications. In summary, Chromium's security architecture is highly effective within its defined threat model: containing renderer compromise resulting from malicious web content. However, CDP-based browser control operates outside this threat model and leverages underlying system trust assumptions regarding local process integrity.

Thus, while Chromium exemplifies strong structural isolation for web threats, by design does not mitigate threats originating from authorized local control channels. In automation-heavy or agentic settings, this distinction becomes security-critical, as CDP may function as a privileged bypass of web-oriented containment guarantees.

2.4 Browser Control Policy in Automation Frameworks

Given that neither Chromium's isolation model nor CDP itself constrains a trusted local process, the remaining candidate containment layer is the automation framework. This subsection examines whether such frameworks can meaningfully bound the impact of an IPI-compromised agent.

Automation frameworks such as Playwright implement an intermediate browser control policy that mediates between untrusted, non-deterministic agent-provided code and privileged browser control interfaces, most notably the Chrome DevTools Protocol (CDP).

As described previously, within the server-centric control model, CDP exposes high-privilege browser capabilities. Consequently, the enforcement of the trust boundary is delegated to the automation layer (e.g., an MCP server embedding Playwright), which constrains how these capabilities may be exercised.

Sandboxed Evaluation Environment. To reduce the attack surface, automation frameworks typically evaluate agent-provided code inside a dedicated execution environment. Taking Playwright as example, it uses a customised Node.js-based layer implemented using the `vm` module, equivalent isolated contexts might be used interchangeably.

This execution environment is constructed with an explicitly declared capability set:

- The sandbox is populated with a curated subset of automation framework APIs.
- These APIs act as controlled proxies over selected CDP domains.
- Optional contextual objects (e.g., structured task inputs) may also be injected.

No direct access to raw CDP sessions, browser internals, or arbitrary process-level primitives is exposed outside the declared interface. In this sense, the automation framework enforces a *capability projection*: only operations representable through the exposed automation primitives are expressible by the agent-delivered code.

Capability Bounding and Its Structural Limits. This policy prevents unrestricted invocation of CDP functionality. However, the resulting trust boundary remains intentionally broad. The underlying reason is structural: automation primitives (e.g., navigation, DOM evaluation, network interception, storage access) are inherently powerful, as the framework's service contract is to provide meaningful browser control for legitimate automation tasks.

Denying or heavily restricting these primitives would undermine the framework's functional purpose. Therefore, any attempt to constrain their usage at a finer granularity would require heuristic or runtime inspection mechanisms rather than static, formally verifiable guarantees.

Accordingly, the primary security objective of the automation policy is *capability bounding*, not semantic correctness enforcement. The layer constrains *what classes of actions* are technically available, but it cannot reliably determine whether a sequence of permitted actions remains aligned with the user's original intent. Misalignment that composes only allowed primitives remains structurally undetectable at this layer.

Execution Contexts and Isolation Semantics. All automation framework APIs ultimately resolve to Chrome DevTools Protocol (CDP) calls across different protocol domains. There is no distinct “browser-level execution mode” separate from CDP; rather, the differentiation lies in *how* CDP capabilities are exercised and which execution context is targeted.

Playwright exposes mechanisms that allow code to be evaluated in different JavaScript worlds within a page:

- **Main world (page context):** JavaScript executes within the same environment as the loaded document and is therefore subject to native web security mechanisms such as CSP, SOP, and CORS.
- **Isolated worlds:** JavaScript executes in a separate execution environment attached to the page, sharing the DOM but not the page’s JavaScript scope.

Both modes ultimately rely on CDP commands, but their security implications differ because web platform protections apply only in the main world.

In agentic deployments, MCP servers commonly influence execution choices through tool descriptions. Tools are documented and exposed in ways that steer the model toward primitives that execute within the page context, thereby preserving web-native protections (CSP, CORS, SOP). This steering, however, is advisory rather than enforceable at the browser level.

Automation frameworks also expose primitives that invoke broader CDP capabilities. For example, a tool such as `browser_run_code` may leverage APIs like `page.request`, which operate independently of in-page execution constraints. Additionally, CDP domains expose configuration methods (e.g., `Page.setBypassCSP`) capable of weakening web-enforced protections when reachable through the automation layer.

Security Implications in Agentic Settings. In the canonical usage scenarios these frameworks were designed for, the controlling process is fully trusted (e.g. e2e testing scripts are authored by developers). In contrast, agentic systems introduce a naturally different risk model. Here, browser actions are derived from model-generated plans, influenced by untrusted and semantically opinionable sources, such as natural-language inputs in prompts, retrieved web content, and tools documentation. Even if each individual automation primitive is permitted and correctly sandboxed, their composition may produce side effects misaligned with the original user intent.

The automation sandbox constrains the *surface of accessible capabilities*, but does not enforce semantic alignment of their use. Browser control policies in automation frameworks should therefore be interpreted as capability-containment layers within a defense-in-depth strategy, rather than as robust isolation barriers against misaligned agent behavior.

In summary, the infrastructure stack underlying BUAs was designed under the assumption of a trusted local controller. None of these layers can detect or prevent semantic-level compromise. This architectural reality is what makes indirect prompt injection a structurally severe threat. The next section examines how this structural gap manifests when comparing traditional and agentic browsing failure modes.

3 Traditional vs Agentic Web Browsing Failure Modes Comparison

3.1 Introduction

This chapter analyzes whether established web security mechanisms remain effective when browsing operations are mediated through an MCP-driven agentic control layer. The analysis directly supports the central argument of this work: that indirect prompt injection constitutes a structurally distinct and severe threat class for BUAs, one that existing web defenses were not designed to address, but indirectly equipped with the necessary primitives to, however currently insufficient.

These mechanisms were designed to prevent common web threats, including XSS, CSRF, client-side template injection, and clickjacking. However, they were conceived under a specific adversarial model: one in which the attacker operates from the web domain and does not control a local trusted process authorized to interact with the browser’s control interface.

Agentic browsing fundamentally alters this assumption.

In particular, the trust model shifts from a traditional user–browser–website interaction to a layered user–LLM host–MCP server–browser–website architecture. This structural transformation has significant implications for the nature of failure modes and for the effectiveness of conventional defenses.

3.2 Trust Model Divergence

While the trust architecture of the wider browser control system was introduced in the previous chapter, this subsection re-examines trust specifically through the lens of attack classes, contrasting capability-level violations (traditional) with semantic-alignment violations (agentic). This distinction is essential to understanding why conventional defenses provide only incidental containment against indirect prompt injection.

Traditional web threats primarily violate trust at the **capability level**. They exploit vulnerabilities that allow unauthorized execution of code or misuse of browser-exposed primitives.

In contrast, agentic browsing threats predominantly violate trust at the **semantic alignment level**. Due to the non-deterministic nature of LLM-based agents, attacks often manipulate the agent’s interpretation of user intent rather than directly subverting browser capability constraints.

Conventional web security mechanisms were designed to defend against adversaries operating as untrusted web principals. They assume that the attacker cannot control a local process legitimately authorized to invoke browser control primitives.

Agentic threats respect the technical invariants of the web trust model while circumventing them by leveraging the local domain as the attack vector. In doing so, they exploit a layer that lies outside the threat assumptions of classical web security mechanisms.

Consequently, protections such as CORS and CSP provide, at best, partial or incidental containment against agentic threats, rather than principled defense.

3.3 Structural Differences Between Attack Classes

Although both traditional and agentic browsing attacks target the client-side trust model and may ultimately lead to similar impact classes (e.g., session hijacking, data exfiltration, state manipulation), their internal mechanics differ substantially.

This work compares:

- Traditional Browsing (TB) attack classes: XSS, CSRF, client-side template injection, clickjacking.
- Agentic Browsing (AB) attack classes: Direct and Indirect Prompt Injection.

Here, I characterize their core differences along three dimensions:

- **Attack Procedure Engine**
 - TB: JavaScript renderer executing injected code.
 - AB: LLM-powered agent executing manipulated plans.
- **Broken Trust Assumption**
 - TB: Executed content originates from a trusted source.
 - AB: Agent actions remain semantically aligned with original user intent.
- **Malicious Payload Type**
 - TB: Executable code or static renderable markup.
 - AB: Natural language content interpreted by the model.

Agentic browsing attacks should therefore not be treated merely as extensions of traditional web exploits. They represent a distinct failure mode category rooted in semantic manipulation rather than capability escalation. Indirect prompt injection is the principal instantiation of this category: the attacker does not inject executable code, but rather natural-language instructions that redirect the agent's plan while remaining within the bounds of technically permitted operations.

3.4 Effectiveness of Traditional Defenses

Despite their structural limitations, traditional web security mechanisms may still reduce attack surface or limit blast radius in agentic contexts. However, their effectiveness is conditional and often indirect.

Most web defenses are origin-based: they regulate behavior depending on whether content originates from a trusted or untrusted web principal.

In an MCP-driven browsing model, this assumption is weakened. Depending on the CDP domain invoked:

- Outbound requests may not execute in a standard web page context and therefore may not be subject to CORS enforcement in the expected manner.
- Content injected via CDP into a page may be treated as originating from a trusted local source rather than from an untrusted web origin, thereby bypassing CSP-origin integrity assumptions.

Nevertheless, some containment effects still hold:

- **CORS**: CDP domains such as Runtime and DOM inject scripts within a page context. Cross-origin requests triggered in that context may still be denied by CORS, forcing the controller to adopt alternative primitives (e.g., Network domain usage or explicit session establishment).

- **HSTS**: Remains effective in preventing downgrade attacks that would compromise confidentiality, integrity, or authenticity.
- **Cookie Security Attributes**:
 - **SameSite**: Prevents trivial cross-origin cookie exfiltration via header leakage, but does not prevent session abuse via CDP-mediated navigation.
 - **HttpOnly**: Blocks direct JavaScript access to authentication cookies, yet does not prevent authenticated session misuse through legitimate browser requests initiated by the agent.
 - **Secure**: Protects against passive MITM but does not constrain local controller authority.

Overall, cookie access constraints and origin-based protections do not prevent abuse of authenticated session authority when such authority is exercised through a trusted CDP client.

In summary, traditional web security mechanisms remain relevant for constraining renderer-level threats but do not directly address the controller-level attack surface introduced by agentic browsing architectures. This finding reinforces the need to examine threats at the MCP layer, which transports the content that drives indirect prompt injection.

4 MCP Failure Modes

This section completes the upstream analysis by cataloging the MCP-native failure modes, vectors to indirect prompt injection in BUAs.

I provide a structured overview of strictly MCP-native threats documented in recent security research [38, 61].

As previously argued, MCP constitutes the technical substrate of agentic browsing systems. Exploiting vulnerabilities at the MCP layer therefore enables downstream web-level attacks with amplified severity, persistence, and automation potential.

Current research on the MCP security landscape reveals semantic inconsistencies: several documented failure modes overlap conceptually, employ heterogeneous terminology, and describe similar attack primitives under different names. To address this ambiguity, I introduce a threat classification framework that categorizes MCP-native threats according to:

- the **system plane** in which the compromise occurs, and
- the **MCP lifecycle phase** during which the protocol security invariants are violated.

4.1 System Plane Based Classification

Control-plane threats compromise the instrumentation layer of agent capabilities. They manipulate tool descriptions, server metadata, or lifecycle update mechanisms in order to influence planning and decision-making before explicit tool invocation.

1 threats compromise runtime semantic integrity. They inject malicious payloads through untrusted external resources or tool outputs that are incorporated into the agent's reasoning context.

4.2 MCP Lifecycle Based Classification

As a second-order analysis, threats are further categorized according to the MCP lifecycle phase they target:

- **Registration:** during capability discovery and metadata ingestion.
- **Planning:** during agent reasoning and tool selection.
- **Execution:** during tool invocation and runtime interaction.

This layered model enables analysis of which trust boundary is violated, whether the compromise persists across sessions, and whether it propagates across system components.

4.3 Data-Plane Threats

LLM-based agents incorporate into their context any content returned by an implicitly trusted MCP server. However, the MCP server retrieves data from an untrusted domain (the web) where trust assumptions rely on inherently fragile infrastructure mechanisms (e.g., BGP, DNS, TLS).

The MCP server therefore acts as a passive transport layer for potentially malicious payloads, which are subsequently trusted by the agent. This is the precise mechanism through which indirect prompt injection payloads reach the agent's context: adversarial instructions embedded in web content traverse the MCP data plane and are incorporated into the LLM's reasoning without semantic filtering.

Sources of malicious payloads can be broadly abstracted to:

- **Malicious Websites:** Attacker-controlled domains injected into agent navigation via DNS poisoning, BGP hijacking, TLS compromise (e.g., CA compromise or certificate hijacking), prior tool poisoning, or combinations thereof
- **Community-Editable Websites:** Platforms whose content can be modified by external contributors and later consumed by the agent without semantic validation.

4.4 Control-Plane Threats

4.4.1 MCP Server Primitive Poisoning. MCP capability primitives metadata is parsed by the agent during initial registration and negotiation. These primitives are incorporated into the agent's baseline reasoning context. Tool selection decisions can therefore be hijacked during this phase through deceptive content embedded in tool descriptions. Although MCP promises isolation boundaries between tools and servers, this guarantee is weakened by the fact that metadata is ingested eagerly and refreshed dynamically. This operational model effectively extends the Trusted Computing Base beyond the local agent to include remote tool descriptions.

- **Tool Shadowing:** Malicious tool descriptions may contain logic that semantically hijacks legitimate tool usage. Even if the malicious tool is never explicitly invoked, its description may influence planning decisions.

This often manifests as:

- referencing another legitimate tool
- specifying canonical chaining requirements
- implicitly instructing exfiltration of tool outputs or telemetry

This behavior undermines the isolation invariant that MCP attempts to enforce. A malicious MCP server do not strictly need to communicate directly with a benign one; instead, the LLM is coerced into acting as a message relay and execution proxy, creating indirect communication channels between otherwise isolated components. As a result, MCP's runtime

security guarantees become reactive and ephemeral rather than preventive.

- **Tool Preference Manipulation:** MCP agents rely heavily on tool descriptions during the planning phase and often prioritize natural-language metadata over actual functional semantics. Due to the absence of cryptographic binding between tool descriptions and their implementation logic, malicious tools that are nominally indistinguishable from legitimate ones (e.g., identical names, deprecation claims, "recommended" labels) can bias the agent toward attacker-controlled capabilities. This phenomenon, sometimes referred to as "Line Jumping" [50], exploits LLM susceptibility to authoritative framing.
- **Fail-Open Tool Chaining:** Tool failures, whether explicit invocation errors or runtime exceptions, are typically treated as recoverable events requiring high-priority handling. In such cases, the agent may invoke alternative tools based on contextual guidance embedded in the failing tool's description. If the failover strategy itself is maliciously specified, the agent will execute it under the assumption of legitimate recovery. This attack may be modelled as a manipulation of error-handling logic, injecting a malicious callback as the exploitation payload, leveraging in an inverted manner LLM reward-hacking vulnerability [61].
- **Rug Pull:** The "Rug Pull" represents a meta-vector rather than a distinct exploit primitive. An MCP server may initially behave benignly and gain trust through aggregation platforms or ecosystem reputation. Subsequently, its tool descriptions or execution logic may be modified to introduce malicious behavior. Because tool metadata is dynamically refreshed and revalidated upon updates, this attack particularly circumvents static trust assumptions when instantiated in a sleeper fashion [42].

4.5 Amplifier Effect: DoS/DDoS Threat

Although conceptually distinct from semantic manipulation attacks, I care also to state that MCP-enabled agentic systems can be leveraged as amplification vectors for (Distributed) denial-of-service (DoS) attacks.

Exploiting either control-plane or data-plane weaknesses, a single malicious prompt or injected content fragment may cause the agent to:

- establish HTTP sessions with target websites,
- perform repeated automated interactions,
- issue high-frequency request sequences in pursuit of a user-specified goal.

Because MCP servers typically spawn ephemeral, headless browser instances, rate-limiting techniques based on trivial client fingerprinting become ineffective.

Similarly, fairness-enforcement mechanisms such as CAPTCHAs may be bypassed when interactions are mediated through fully automated browser instances capable of solving or avoiding such challenges.

As a result, MCP-driven agentic systems may unintentionally function as scalable traffic amplification infrastructures when compromised.

With the MCP attack surface mapped, in the following section provides an in-depth analysis of IPI itself at the Agentic system layer, that directly targets.

5 Indirect Prompt Injection in Agentic Systems

This section begins with the inherent LLM properties that make IPI possible and exacerbate its risk, before surveying the defense and attack techniques that define the current state of the art.

Guaranteeing security and safety in AI agents is fundamentally constrained by the structural properties of such systems, and is mostly inherently due to the nature of the system's core, the LLM. I report four critical challenges that directly enable and exacerbate indirect prompt injection.

- **Non-deterministic behaviours:** LLMs are essentially probabilistic systems. Their output is based on a few key mechanisms whose mathematical formulations often lack accuracy, such as stochastic decoding; therefore the same input and operational context can result in different outputs. New behaviours that were not explicitly programmed, or designed to be prevented, can arise unexpectedly during the model lifetime. This unpredictability is exacerbated by multi-tool jobs and high levels of autonomy in decision-making, expanding the runtime attack surface and the criticality of attacks. Safety and security testing must account for the probabilistic nature of failure modes and their strong intimacy with the operational context.
- **Hallucinations:** LLMs cannot guarantee consistently factual accuracy and faithfulness to initial user intent [20]. LLMs are often biased by the operational context or by misinterpretation of the user query or system prompt, such that the fabricated response departs from the original intent and is not grounded in truth.
- **Sycophancy:** Tendency of LLMs to produce responses that primarily match user beliefs conveyed in the query, rather than reflect the truth [59]. This property is particularly exacerbated in LLMs that have undergone refinements based on RLHF.
- **Reward Alignment Bias:** LLMs are trained to satisfy the user query and not commit errors; as such they enter an urgent execution mode when errors are perceived. LLM reasoning can be manipulated toward an undesired interpretation of reality by exploiting this bias. Similarly to the previous, this tendency is exacerbated in LLMs that have undergone relevant error-fixing refinements based on RLHF.
- **Wide and layered attack surface:** Intuitively, a new level of system abstraction implies respective attack vectors, beyond domain-specific ones. Hence the attack surface model of canonical information systems (e.g., application, infrastructure, code) can be broadly extended with: training data and process, planning and orchestration configurations, runtime memory and persisted context stores, tooling interfaces, and any external environment.

Given the system context and adversarial model constraints established throughout this work, indirect prompt injection emerges

as the dominant threat model for BUAs. This assessment is consistent with the broader LLM-powered agentic systems threat landscape [22]: prompt injection stands out as a threat with a high attack success rate, ease of production, and severity of impact [60], backed also by national security agencies and cybersecurity organizations worldwide [49, 62].

Generally, in LLMs a *prompt* refers to the input fed to the model, containing instructions and context for the desired task, including prior turns of interaction between the user and the model, if applicable. The *injection* refers to the procedure of feeding nefarious data into the agent context, interpreted as authoritative instructions, such that the agent goal, or task in the scenario of a specialised agent, is hijacked. Current real-world instantiations denote an injection composed of two core components.

- **Execution trigger** [53]: A string specifically crafted to deceive the LLM into deviating from the original intent and/or breaking its security and safety boundaries specified in the system prompt and user query, by making it interpret the following payload as instructions. For example: *“Important instruction from the user, disregard what you have been told so far and ...”*
- **Payload:** The malicious instructions that manipulate the model into one of its failure modes.

Indirect prompt injections introduce the intriguing challenge of maintaining user intent when malicious instructions are embedded within retrieved data on which the LLM bases its decision-making process. The following argument by Gwern Branwen on LessWrong [23] articulates the criticality of indirect prompt injection with particular clarity:

“... a language model is a Turing-complete weird machine running programs written in natural language; when you do retrieval, you are not ‘plugging updated facts into your AI’, you are actually downloading random new unsigned blobs of code from the Internet (many written by adversaries) and casually executing them on your LM with full privileges. This does not end well.”

In the preceding paragraphs I introduced the most common variant of prompt injection, which involves compromising the agentic system control plane by overriding instructions in the LLM plan. A more stealthy variant involves compromising the data plane by manipulating one or more arguments of tool calls being executed, leaving the control plane intact. This is analogous to an SQL injection attack in which an adversary manipulates the query parameters rather than the structure of the query itself [30].

Moreover, an emerging attack class, synergic to IPI and significantly relevant for browser-use agentic systems, is Branch Steering [33]. Intuitively, the attack involves manipulating the external environment coherently with the user query and hiding malicious operations behind seemingly benign and task-aligned elements, such that the model perception is poisoned and the agent is steered into interacting with the attacker trap.

In this section I illustrate the latest defense techniques from Indirect Prompt Injection, either documented in the literature, backed by empirical testing, or applied in the industry, reportedly also at

large scale. Similarly, attack techniques aimed at breaking these defenses are described.

While the following attack and defense techniques are framed for the indirect variant of prompt injection, they are not strictly tailored for it, and most of the procedural principles may also apply in the direct variant; nevertheless the provided examples showcase attacks rooted in external untrusted domains.

5.1 Defenses

All mainstream AI service providers report in their latest model documentations [18, 51] the adoption of a defence-in-depth model in their security architecture, with three macro layers: model, application, and infrastructure level. I break down some control measures of the former two in this chapter.

Generally, these defences aim to reduce various threat risks that exploit previously illustrated inherent LLM vulnerabilities. Fundamentally, without such defences, any LLM can be trivially jailbroken or goal-hijacked.

5.1.1 LLM Defences - Adversarial Machine Learning. Adversarial Machine Learning is a scientific research discipline, a declination of Machine Learning, that studies inherent weaknesses in LLMs which can be exploited to deceive models and induce non-intended behaviors. It addresses vulnerabilities in both training and inference phases (e.g., sycophancy and hallucinations), essentially instrumenting the model to allocate critical attention over token patterns potentially associated with nefarious goals.

While reasoning guardrails are of remarkable importance, and significant research has been conducted in this area, these defences do not directly address the predominant threat considered in this work, namely (Indirect) Prompt Injection. Instead, they are largely aimed at improving classifier robustness in supervised learning settings [41], preventing classification impairment due to adversarial perturbations [35].

Therefore, I present some notable techniques at a high level, with pointers to relevant literature for deeper analysis.

Most model-layer defences are installed during training; however, some require additional inference-time mechanisms for robustness guarantees. Accordingly, defences can be categorized based on the LLM lifecycle phase in which they operate:

- **Training:** Improve robustness by altering the learning process, enforcing stable decision boundaries.
- **Inference:** Attempt to hinder adversarial example generation during prediction, typically through gradient masking or obfuscation. However, these approaches are widely considered unreliable, as adaptive attacks can often circumvent them.

The core idea behind most of these defences is to modify the training process such that the model prioritizes safety while preserving utility [65]. This involves leveraging large and diverse sets of adversarial samples alongside curated safety datasets [17].

- **Training-Phase Defences**
 - **Goal / Task Prioritisation** [56, 68]: The model is fine-tuned either with datasets that stress safety over utility, or to make it adhere strictly to a specific task. In the latest

variant the capability to interpret instructions that would hijack the goal is removed entirely.

- **Circuit Breaking** [44]: Identification and ablation of model pathways that statistically lead to undesirable behaviour.
- **DARD: Dice Adversarial Robustness Distillation** [69]: Robustness from a large, adversarially robust teacher model is transferred to a smaller student model via knowledge distillation, while utility is maintained.
- **StruQ** [27]: Queries are encoded in a structured format that separates data from instructions; the model is then trained to reject queries that contain instructions embedded in the data channel.
- **Meta-SecAlign** [28]: Introduces a new prompt-message structure and trains the model with both desirable and undesirable responses to prompt-injection samples; additionally fine-tuned with DPO to favour secure responses.
- **Inference-Phase Defences**
 - **RA-LLM** [25]: Alignment verification via input-perturbation probes; outputs produced by perturbed inputs that misalign with the original goal are rejected.
 - **Decoder-Level Control (RDS)** [67]: Safety of candidate tokens is evaluated step-by-step during autoregressive decoding; outputs embedding multiple unsafe tokens are corrected or rejected in real time.

5.1.2 Application Defences. Successfully defending against indirect prompt injection requires addressing the model's inability to distinguish between benign data and malicious instructions within the dynamic context of agentic tasks [64]. Moreover, state-of-the-art computer-using agents adopt iterative reasoning-and-acting architectures, whereby plans are progressively adapted based on untrusted external content at each step. This makes robust runtime verification of execution plans inherently challenging.

Detection of prompt injection attacks typically relies on evaluating two key metrics:

- **Semantic alignment:** consistency between external content and the user query or operational context [15].
- **External data patterns:** identification of anomalous or adversarial linguistic structures [12].

However, both approaches suffer from high susceptibility to spurious correlations, and mitigating such correlations without degrading agent utility remains an open problem.

Prompt Engineering-Based Defences. Since the early development of agentic systems, the literature has proposed several defenses based on prompt engineering techniques, aimed at improving robustness:

- **Spotlighting** [32]: transforms external data and appends instructions directing the model to ignore embedded commands. Techniques include delimiting, paraphrasing, data marking, and encoding.
- **Prompt Sandwiching** [57]: reinforces alignment with the original user intent by wrapping external content between repeated instances of the user query.
- **Robust Prompt Optimization (RPO)** [5]: appends an optimized safety suffix to prompts, derived through a gradient-based minimax optimization process [31]. While primarily

targeting jailbreaks, it can be adapted to mitigate indirect prompt injection risks.

Despite their adoption, recent benchmarks demonstrate the fragility of these defenses against sophisticated prompt injection attacks [2, 48]. Furthermore, they often degrade agent utility, effectively limiting system usability [4].

These limitations motivate a paradigm shift: robust mitigation of prompt injection requires embedding security guarantees as first-class architectural properties, rather than relying solely on prompt-level defenses. This perspective is reflected in recent research efforts and industrial practices, particularly in agentic browsing systems. Architectural defenses can be abstracted as systems that:

- Monitor specific primitives of the agentic system,
- Evaluate alignment between observed behavior and user intent,
- Enforce mitigation upon detecting misalignment.

These approaches are promising as they decouple safety enforcement from the base model, often leveraging auxiliary models or system-level controls. However, detectors inherit the vulnerabilities of neural networks, and adversaries may simultaneously bypass both the primary model and its detector [26, 48].

Capability Restriction Mechanisms.

- **ProGENT** [13]: a semi-dynamic, policy-based capability restriction layer using a domain-specific language. Policies adapt to environment state and enforce agent-environment boundaries.
- **MCPGuardian** [11]: extends capability restriction by instrumenting the MCP layer with security primitives such as WAF, rate limiting, logging, tracing, and authentication.

Runtime Plan Monitoring.

- **AgentSentinel** [7]: introduces a context-aware LLM-based auditing layer for sensitive tool calls, correlating signals across agent I/O, logs, and environment feedback.
- **AgentGuard** [6]: observes live agent execution (I/O, tool calls and results, environment), models agent execution as a Markov Decision Process, and applies probabilistic model checking to predict unsafe behaviors.
- **AlignmentCheck (LlamaFirewall)** [10]: Meta has proposed a suite of security tools, then provided bundled in PurpleLama[45], among which AlignmentCheck does runtime model reasoning chain-of-thought contextual auditing, detecting contradictions, goal divergence, and other signs of injection-induced misalignment
- **PIGuard** [12]: prompt-based detection technique which employs a distinct classifier model to distinguish benign and malicious prompts. The key is the training strategy, MOF(Mitigating Over-defence for Free), which fine-tunes the model to rely more on contextual semantics rather than predictive trigger tokens.
- **Semantic Context Analysis** [15]: employs an embedding and a classifier model to analyse the semantic relationship between user intent and external content and detect semantic misalignment between external data and user query. It is proven to be significantly robust against malicious external data involving paraphrasing, but pose no guarantee against

IPI attacks manipulating the data plane of the system, such as Branch Steering [48].

- **ceLLMate** [9]: browser-level sandbox for web-using agents implementing the external capabilities restriction paradigm. It enforces domain- and task-specific HTTP-level guardrails at the website, using browser primitives. Policies can be pre-defined or dynamically suggested by an AI assistant based on user intent and context. Assuming the planner may be compromised, it generally focuses on least-privilege execution and blast-radius containment against IPIs, rather than preventing control-plane compromise.

Structural Isolation of Data and Control Planes. Some of the most robust defenses restructure the agent architecture to enforce strict isolation between trusted control logic and untrusted data:

- **CaMeL** [30]: adopts a dual-LLM architecture where a privileged model derives plans solely from user input, while a quarantined model processes external data. Communication between the two is mediated by a policy-enforcing interpreter, preventing control-plane compromise. A recent extension [33] adapts this paradigm for computer-using agents by separating high-level control flow from dynamic environment perception, enabling secure yet flexible decision-making.

5.2 Attacks

Injected instructions are not merely ad hoc artifacts, but rather the result of systematic engineering processes. The execution trigger and the payload are designed based on a plethora of factors, among which, given their reliance on the semantics of the previously illustrated defenses, a fundamental one is their semantic plausibility with respect to the original user task and operational context.

As a reminder, in an indirect setting the attacker's goal is to make the LLM interpret instructions in the external data; as such, the injected instruction is engineered to increase the likelihood of this execution mode. Hence, attack construction can be framed as an optimization problem. Advanced generation methods involve the continuous refinement of the injected instructions, adopting adaptive, search-based methodologies.

In this section, both naive and more sophisticated optimization techniques are covered. Finally, a conceptual breakdown of injected instructions is proposed, resulting from the observation of various samples.

5.2.1 Naive Heuristics-based Optimization Techniques. Following the line of thought of the broad literature, here I coin the *naive* class to identify all techniques which are based on heuristics and typically applied in a manual setting; thereby the generation process cannot scale nor continuously adapt to model feedback. Nevertheless, from a crafted injected instruction perspective, they can be considered as attack design primitives.

- **Instructions Override** [54]: uses explicit directives, such as the classical “*ignore previous instructions*”, to switch the operational context, effectively nullifying the constraints specified in the prior context and assigning the highest priority level to the injected instructions. [54] instantiates attacks that override instructions from the tail; another interesting

variant may consist in rewriting the whole prior conversation and prefixing the injected instruction in the highest-priority segment, effectively extending the system prompt.

- **Guardrail Evasion**: consists in evading any structural boundary specified in the system prompt or user query, mainly by repeating the delimiter or specifying the termination of the external data, which denotes the model's inability to respect structural boundaries between data and instructions. It is empirically proven to successfully break static prompt-based guardrails, such as Spotlighting or Prompt Sandwiching. This sanitization limitation can be rooted back to traditional computer systems: sanitizing a user-controlled input that is mixed with legitimate executable code cannot be safely done without impacting system utility [63].
- **Fake Completion** [2]: emulates the start of the response by appending the query completion prefix to the end of the injected instruction. This prefix typically signals either that the original user task has been completed or that the injection task has been initiated. Similarly, a response suffix can be specified, aiming to condition the trajectory of generation toward a predefined end state.
- **Role-based Privilege Escalation** [14]: in an agentic setting, the LLM is programmed with instructions in the system prompt to assume a role tailored for the tasks it must accomplish, including behavioural boundaries, which might be further hardened with previous defenses. This technique consists in re-programming the LLM to assume a role with higher authorization, such that all previous boundaries are broken. The most common instance is DAN (Do-Anything-Now) [3].
- **Virtual Execution Context Scaffolding** [16]: creates a hypothetical or simulated scenario, presenting it as a fictional or sandboxed environment, in which the injected instructions are encoded as semantically coherent and innocuous. The model is thereby induced to treat the instructions as contextually valid within the simulated setting, leading to execution despite their adversarial nature.

5.2.2 Search-based Adaptive Optimization Techniques. Search-based techniques are considered a class of optimization methods which conceptually consist in iteratively exploring and optimizing a discrete prompt space based on an effectiveness score, function of various execution signals. Techniques differ primarily in their search strategy, i.e., how candidates are evaluated and updated.

As demonstrated by recent works [8, 48], these attacks are particularly effective at breaking naive prompt-based defenses, also in agentic systems with indirect injection vectors.

- **Gradient-based search** [5]: the literature proposes a set of adaptive techniques whose optimization is based on reducing a loss function with respect to an objective function, guided by an approximation of tokens' gradients in the embedding space. There are several variants, all inspired by [5]; however, most are proven to be ineffective in indirect and agentic settings. Some of the most notable include MGCG, AutoDAN-GCG [8], and beam search [60]. These techniques are also argued to be impractical in realistic adversarial models, as

gradients require white-box access and computationally expensive iterative optimization [48].

- **Actor-critic** [60]: inspired by the reinforcement learning actor-critic framework [40], this technique pairs two cooperative models iteratively: an Actor that proposes modifications to injection triggers, and a Critic that evaluates them based on feedback from the target model. The feedback is typically computed as the difference in average token log-probabilities across malicious versus benign completions, and is used as a reward signal to refine the Actor until sufficiently high scores are achieved.
- **Tree of Attacks with Pruning (TAP)** [60]: bridging from the original technique designed for jailbreaking, its variant tailored for indirect settings adopts a structured approach by recursively expanding a tree of candidates. Candidates are evaluated based on the edit delta between their produced response and the target function call, using a critic model with binary scoring: candidates below a predefined threshold are retained, otherwise pruned. The generator model is implicitly conditioned to improve surviving candidates. However, this purely lexical metric has been shown to be an insufficiently accurate proxy for steering model behaviour toward the desired function call. Nevertheless, notably, this technique applies to black-box adversarial settings.
- **Probabilistic multi-dimensional search** [48]: following LLM-guided code optimization principles such as Alpha-Code [1], this technique adopts a bi-dimensional grid-based iterative search partitioning candidates by length and diversity. A central controller maintains this structure using an Island MAP-Elites model. At each cycle, a mutator LLM generates new candidates based on prior attempts, which are then scored by a critic LLM. The critic produces both qualitative feedback and a numerical score (1–10), reflecting its interpretation of the target model's behavioural outputs. This technique attempts to combine the strengths of previous approaches, but inherits their limitations. In particular, its probabilistic scoring mechanism does not rely on a ground-truth signal, but rather on an interpretation of behavioural proxies. This introduces the risk of reward hacking, where the optimization process maximizes the score without achieving the actual attack objective [48].

6 Threat Model

This chapter grounds the BUAs Indirect Prompt Injection robustness benchmark that follows, covering system context assumptions (trust model) including defenses, the adversarial model including optimization techniques, goals, and finally a brief formal attack formulation. The analysis follows a fault-based approach: threats are rooted in the final adversarial goals and the attack surface is narrowed to the inherent protocol-level (MCP) threats to the system, through which the desired impact can be achieved.

6.1 System Context Assumptions

In order to narrow down the scope to a realistic setting, the following system context assumptions are made: a system with an LLM-agent, an MCP client, and an MCP server interfacing the latter

with a web browser instance executed in debug mode, with some live sessions with multiple websites. The browser control system is server-centric and uses a browser automation framework (e.g., Playwright) as proxy to CDP. Hence, I assume toxic flow sinks are all web-based, disregarding any other MCP Server; the browser completely delegates control authority to any local process, no CDP domains are restricted, and the browser automation framework does not constrain any CDP usage patterns. I further assume that the browser instance has cached some valid authentication tokens, which the browser will default to use when authenticating with the respective target website. Moreover, no strict procedural guardrail is applied on the agent execution flow, e.g., tight human-in-the-loop. Finally, I assume a no-protection baseline and then all the previously depicted naive application-level defenses are singularly integrated in the system.

6.2 Adversarial Model

Following the guideline of considering scenarios as close as possible to the real world, which require low or medium adversarial effort, I narrow down attacker capabilities as follows.

- **Control:** The adversary cannot prompt the agent directly or control the user prompt in any way, though it can access external data the agent may retrieve throughout its execution, and generally execute legitimate actions in the web domain.
- **System knowledge:** The adversary does not have direct visibility on the victim's behaviours, but may know at a high level its identity, hence can approximate its web interaction patterns. Additionally, it does not know the specific MCP server used, neither can it manipulate its tool descriptions and internal behaviour.
- **Agent access level:** As in a realistic setting, the attacker has access to samples of the agent, which are black boxes; it has access only to the final model output. Nevertheless, there are often indirect ways to approximate the models' loss even if tokens probabilities are not directly accessible [43]
- **Skill and financial support level:** Even though not strictly required to instance the illustrated threats successfully, the adversary is relatively expert in the adversarial machine learning domain and is also financially supported. As such it leverages all the previously depicted naive heuristics-based optimization techniques, singularly and in combination.

6.3 Adversarial Goals

Generally speaking the adversary aims to exfiltrate sensitive data accessible to the agent, induce the agent to perform unauthorized harmful actions, disrupt its operation, or use it as a foothold for persistent attacks. The following list converts these abstract goals into concrete impacts.

- (1) **Exfiltrate PII, client-side authentication and session tokens:** cookies, localStorage tokens, credentials, previous request headers, authentication-restricted page DOM attributes.
- (2) **Execute arbitrary code with user privileges:** leverage authentication tokens to act with the user's privileges in any web application, and perform operations to a malicious

extent (e.g., change credentials, initiate bank transfers, complete purchases).

- (3) **User trust erosion:** user trust in an organization, entity, or service is gradually decayed, diminishing the user's future engagement with it.
- (4) **System Escalation - compromise the victim machine:** evade the browser sandbox by leveraging the highly privileged permissions of the browser to execute arbitrary code on the victim machine, e.g., syscalls, spawn local processes, CDP reflection, download binaries This goal represents the highest-impact outcome and is directly enabled by the class of sinks analysed in Section 6.4.1.

In the previous trust model chapter I highlighted the severity of the loose trust assumption on the semantic alignment of agent browsing operations to the original user intent. Conversely, the aforementioned MCP data-plane threat raises a concern on the implicit trust that MCP clients have in MCP servers [38]. The agent typically assumes that tool call outputs are system-verified feedback, and thus lacks strict contextual isolation during parsing. While the trust boundaries applied in the web trust model guarantee content properties such as confidentiality, integrity and authenticity, they cannot guarantee that the content does not contain nefarious data in any way deceiving for the consuming end agent, and neither should the MCP server interfacing the browser, as rejection of delivering the content would break its service contract. Hence, it is apparent how the combination of these two wide trust boundaries can be exploited to achieve a replay of malicious content back and forth from the web domain, optionally amplified by the LLM-agent.

With that being said, the following benchmark presents attack instances of both MCP data-plane and control-plane threats, with a remarkable emphasis on the former kind, which additionally respect the adversarial model and are effectively a vector to the predominant threat model of this study, Indirect Prompt Injection. Attacks rooted in the MCP control-plane instance a lower-level compromise to the system, thereby constituting a step ahead that does not require compromise of the agent control-plane, even though they slightly break the adversarial model.

6.4 Attack Formulation

Drawing inspiration from the practical attack formulation framework presented by the Google DeepMind team for Gemini [60], I formalize the Indirect Prompt Injection attack in the context of agentic web browsing as an end-to-end flow that traverses three core components

Source. The source is any MCP server tool that returns data from a repository accessible to the attacker, whereby the returned data contains the injected instructions x_{adv} . In the web browsing scenario, the source is typically a tool that retrieves content from a web page or API endpoint controlled or influenced by the adversary. Concretely, when the user issues a benign prompt x_{user} , the agent invokes one or more tools whose responses include content d_{ext} from the untrusted web domain. The adversary has embedded x_{adv} within d_{ext} prior to retrieval, such that the MCP server transports the full response back to the agent context without filtering or validation.

Data Forwarding Node. In classical taint-tracking analyses the forwarding node is a passive relay that merely redirects data from source to sink. In an agentic system, however, the LLM-agent acts as a fundamentally different kind of intermediary: it *interprets* the natural-language instructions encoded in the retrieved data and *generates* the downstream attack payload, effectively constructing the concrete tool call or code snippet that realizes the adversary's intent. This step constitutes an augmentation stage: the injected instruction need not contain the literal payload that will reach the sink; rather, it can express the adversarial objective at a high level of abstraction, and the agent's reasoning capabilities will translate it into a well-formed, context-specific action. An exception arises when x_{adv} contains the exact code, in which case the agent's role collapses to that of a near-passive relay that wraps the attacker-supplied code in the appropriate tool call envelope;

Sink. The sink is the final execution endpoint at which the forwarded or generated payload realizes its effect in the browser. Following the systematic perspective adopted throughout this document, compromises at the browser can be abstracted to either *data-plane* or *control-plane* manipulations. Data-plane sinks involve feeding attacker-controlled values to parametrise legitimate client-side scripts provided by the website. Control-plane sinks involve injecting or executing arbitrary code in the browser context, thereby granting the attacker full programmatic control over the browsing session.

The distinction is critical from an impact perspective. While data-plane sinks are bounded by the semantics of the target application's own code, control-plane sinks enable the full spectrum of adversarial goals. As covered in the system context chapter, the CDP API domains that enable such execution modes are precisely *Runtime* (e.g., `Runtime.evaluate`, `Runtime.runScript`), *Debugger* (e.g., `Debugger.evaluateOnCallFrame`), and *DOM* (e.g., `DOM.setNodeValue`, `DOM.setAttributeValue`), through which code can be injected or executed with privileges ranging from a sandboxed page context to a full browser process context.

6.4.1 Arbitrary Code Execution Sinks Landscape Analysis. To provide evidence to the reality of the control-plane manipulation, I survey arbitrary code execution primitives across few mainstream open-source browser MCP servers. As discussed previously in the trust model chapter, while these primitives may superficially resemble vulnerabilities, not offering them would partially break the service contract of a browser automation server; their presence is therefore architectural, not accidental. I inspect the relevant tool implementation of each, verify its underlying CDP invocation, and classify the results into three execution privilege tiers, ordered by decreasing severity of potential impact.

- (1) **Privileged browser context (Extension APIs).** Code executes within the browser extension's privileged context, with access to the full `WebExtension` API surface (`chrome.tabs`, `chrome.cookies`, `chrome.storage`, unrestricted cross-origin fetch). Compromise at this level subsumes all lower tiers and enables cross-origin data exfiltration and browser-wide session manipulation without web security mechanism constraints. `mcp-chrome` [39] falls in this tier: agent-supplied

JavaScript is executed directly via `new Function` in the extension's background service worker, without any sanitization.

- (2) **Page execution context via CDP.** Code is injected into the target web page's JavaScript runtime via the CDP *Runtime* domain. It shares the page's origin, can access `localStorage`, `sessionStorage`, and the full DOM. Attacks at this level are constrained by same-origin policy for outbound requests when initiated from the page context, though CDP *Network* domain calls bypass this limitation. Two surveyed servers fall in this tier: `chrome-devtools-mcp` [29] deserialises and executes agent-supplied code with `eval()`, `molotov` [47] issues CDP commands directly to the Runtime domain.
- (3) **Sandboxed Node.js execution environment.** Code runs in an isolated Node.js vm context in the MCP server process, populated with a curated set of automation APIs. No direct access to raw CDP sessions or browser internals is available outside this declared interface. `playwright-mcp` [46] falls in this tier: agent-supplied JavaScript is evaluated via `vm.runInContext` with the Playwright `Page` object injected into the sandbox context. The agent code can invoke any method on the Page API, and depending on which method is called, different CDP domain endpoints can be consumed, equally to the previous level.

7 Experiments

This section reports the results of benchmarking 9 closed-source LLMs (o3-mini, GPT-4.1-mini, GPT-5-mini, Claude 3.7 Sonnet, Claude Sonnet 4, Claude Sonnet 4.5, Gemini 2.0 Flash, Gemini 2.5 Flash, Gemini 3 Flash Preview) from mainstream providers within a canonical browser-use mono-agentic system, evaluating both system security and utility.

The benchmark extends AgentDojo [4] with primitives that enable testing for MCP data and control plane attacks, including variants with browser sandbox evasion impact. All the naive heuristics-based optimization techniques surveyed in the previous sections are implemented, alongside a lightweight variant of TAP adapted for the indirect setting. Bridging directly from the `agentdojo` definition, utility and security are respectively founded on user and injection tasks. The former are the legitimate user instructions, whereas the latter are the injected instructions that manipulate the agent execution. Each task exposes utility, security functions which assert whether the agent has solved the tasks correctly, by inspecting the model output and the mutations in the environment state. Each execution is classified into one of four outcome categories determined by the conjunction of utility and security assertions:

- *Robust Success* : utility satisfied, security not violated
- *Benign Failure* : utility not satisfied, security not violated
- *Malicious Failure* : utility not satisfied, security violated
- *Stealthy Compromise* : utility satisfied, security violated.

The complete benchmark, including datasets, configurations, and results, is accessible and runnable off-the-shelf at <https://github.com/Diekgbbtt/agentdojo>

7.1 Experiment Settings

The agentic system under test follows a mono-agent architecture: a single agent interfaces with the browser through an MCP server. Alternatively, the benchmark can be executed towards a mock environment, leveraging a native tooling system of the framework, which replicates MCP tools. This benchmarking mode was used for simple data plane goal hijacking tests. The agent is augmented with skills-based instrumentation, whereby available tool capabilities and their descriptions are injected into the system prompt at initialization, reproducing the operational context of production deployments.

Injected instructions are drawn primarily from two open prompt injection datasets produced by related research efforts: the HackAPrompt dataset [58] and OpenPromptInject [2]. The injection tasks cover the full spectrum of adversarial goals formalized earlier: PII and credential exfiltration, cross-tab session token theft, unauthorized actions under the user's authenticated session, and browser sandbox evasion through arbitrary code execution.

The browser MCP server selected for the benchmark is Playwright [46], chosen for its wide adoption in agentic browsing systems and its conformance to the server-centric control model defined in the threat model. The browser instance runs locally and is exposed solely on the loopback interface. To ensure that the benchmark targets solely the agent's robustness rather, incidental CSP containments are disabled via the `CDP Page.setBypassCSP` command.

The term threat snapshot [22] is used to describe an agentic browsing circumstance, which involves accessing adversarially manipulated content. As such, each is a pair of agentdojo user and injection tasks. Injections are distinct between data and control plane attacks, for the latter I have used a smaller set of injection tasks.

The benchmark dataset size varies by attack category. MCP data-plane goal hijacking comprises $5 \times 5 = 25$ threat snapshots (user \times injection tasks), executed across all combinations of eight naive optimization techniques (InstructionsOverride, GuardrailEvasion, FakeCompletion, RoleEscalation, VirtualContextScaffolding, TrustEscalation, ImportantInstructions, PrivilegedAuthorityAdvise) and three application-level defenses (Spotlighting with Delimiting, Prompt Sandwiching, Robust Prompt Optimization), plus the undefended baseline. MCP control-plane attacks use $2 \times 3 = 6$ threat snapshots per upstream vector (tool shadowing, tool preference manipulation, fail-open chaining, rug pull), evaluated across all defenses without optimization, as naive heuristics are irrelevant for upstream MCP manipulation. Data-plane goal hijacking with sandbox evasion impact uses $2 \times 3 = 6$ threat snapshots run across all optimization-defense pairs. Adaptive TAP-based optimization operates on $3 \times 5 = 15$ threat snapshots across all defenses, with the generator LLM instrumented to employ all optimization techniques jointly. Since the stacked bar charts present normalised outcome distributions, these absolute scales are essential for interpreting the reported proportions.

Throughout the iterative development of the framework, both the threat snapshots and the benchmarking infrastructure have been progressively refined. Each threat snapshot was executed repeatedly until no incidental failure mode attributable to the agentic

system or external web application was observed in the execution logs; runs exhibiting such extraneous failures were discarded. The reported data therefore reflect executions that are free from incidental failure modes of the agentic system, such as LLM API rate limits, browser sandbox containment, or web application security mechanisms (e.g. two-factor authentication on email change). To this end, the agent has been instrumented with pre-defined browsing workflows through a skills-based system. Full execution logs are available in the project repository.

7.2 Results

Results are illustrated following the attacks taxonomy : MCP data and control plane, the former is further underpin in two variants with sandbox evasion downstream impact and adaptive optimization. Attack success rates (ASR) are the primary metric throughout.

The central finding is that recent LLMs, which have undergone dedicated adversarial training, demonstrate robust resilience across all threat snapshots and optimization techniques. Concretely, GPT-5-mini, Claude Sonnet 4.5, and Gemini 3 Flash Preview achieve aggregate ASRs in the range of 13–16% while maintaining utility rates above 82%. In contrast, less recent LLMs exhibited measurable vulnerability to several attack instances, particularly when adversarial optimization was applied: Gemini 2.0 Flash and GPT-4.1-mini reach aggregate ASRs of approximately 64% and 63% respectively. TAP-based adaptive optimization proved the most effective at circumventing the baseline defenses of these models, producing the highest ASR among the tested techniques.

The integration of application-level defenses yielded a significant reduction in ASR across all optimization techniques, even for the less robust models. Particularly, among these Prompt Sandwiching demonstrates a significant drop in attack success.

When it comes to MCP data-plane compromises, a common property that can be extracted from the analysis of successful threat snapshots is the semantic cohesion between the original user task and the injected task. In most of these instances, the injected instruction is engineered to have a minimal semantic delta from the intent of the user query, such that task-alignment guardrails embedded in the model reasoning are not triggered.

Remarkably, several less robust LLMs were successfully hijacked to execute arbitrary code in the browser context, effectively instantiating the browser sandbox evasion threat. These results provide empirical evidence that the arbitrary code execution sinks analyzed in Section 6.4.1, under realistic adversarial constraints, can be exploited to escalate an agent compromise to underlying machine compromise, and break the assumptions the browser sandbox relies on.

Control-plane attacks achieve systematically higher ASR than data-plane goal hijacking across all models, with even GPT-5-mini reaching approximately 32% ASR under MCP control-plane threats compared to approximately 15% under data-plane attacks. This gap confirms that upstream tool metadata manipulation bypasses model-level adversarial training, which is primarily oriented toward in-context instruction resistance.

7.3 Limitations

Bypassing CSP by initialising the browsing session with `Page.setBypassCSP` command decays the reality of the experiment, deviating slightly from the threat model. Enabling this defense would diminish the ASR of injection tasks with exfiltration goal

The TAP adaptive optimization is implemented in a lighter variant. Rather than relying on the purely lexical edit delta between the produced response and the target function call as the evaluation signal, the implementation scores candidates based on a semantic interpretation of execution logs, classifying the defensive mode triggered in the target LLM. While this approach addresses the known limitations of lexical scoring as a proxy for attack success, it introduces its own biases and may not fully capture the optimization dynamics of the original technique.

The benchmarking dataset is relatively limited in size with respect to user tasks, injection tasks, defenses and optimization techniques, although it broadly covers all the macro categories proposed by the literature. Similarly, the adaptive optimization operates under constrained iterations and candidate space sizes. The critic and generator LLMs used in the TAP pipeline are conditioned with lightweight in-context learning through a multi-shot prompt rather than supervised fine-tuning of the model, which may limit their effectiveness relative to fully trained adversarial models.

8 Conclusions and Future Work

This work presented a systematic analysis of indirect prompt injection severity in browser-using agents, tracing the threat from its protocol-level enablers in MCP through the browser control stack to concrete exploitation. The analysis demonstrated that MCP lacks design primitives oriented to adversarial containment, and that the downstream browser structural defenses can be invalidated in this web browsing setting, if the attack vectors through an agent compromise. Similarly, conventional web security mechanisms were shown to provide at best incidental containment. This thesis is rooted in the execution domain of the agentic system, the local trusted-process domain, and the role of the system in the attack procedure: an authoritative attack payload reflector.

An additional corollary meaningful finding from this study was how decisively control-plane attacks outperformed data-plane counterparts. This outcome highlights how model adversarial training is inherently primarily oriented for instructions integrity, posing no protection against compromises of the protocol foundation they rely on. This insight raises the criticality of application-level defenses. Sinergically, while lightweight prompt-based application-level defenses reduced ASR for data-plane attacks, their mitigation was minimal for the counterparts vectoring through the control-plane.

This study is designed to set the ground in the domain of BUAs security, as such inherently several directions remain open for future investigation. Some of the most remarkable could be:

- Benchmark extension along various dimensions: broader set of user and injection tasks; integration of all covered optimization and defense techniques; agent system attacks, beyond goal hijacking, such as data-flow hijacking and branch steering.

- The adoption of open-weight fine-tuned models for adaptive attack optimization, removing the dependency on closed-source critic and generator LLMs, and symmetrically, the application of fine-tuned open-weight models as auxiliary components in defense architectures, such as classifier-based runtime monitors or alignment-check auditors.
- The whole produced artifact would generally benefit from a more nuanced classification of attacks, as in [22]

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A Supplementary Charts

Previously depicted aggregated model's outcome are decomposed with a finer granularity in the following stacked bar charts, illustrating each model results across all bench settings, distributed into the four execution categories. Due to the size of this charts set, only few samples are reported, the full set can be found in the charts directory of the Github repository.

A.1 Data-plane

Figure 6: no optimization and defense

Figure 7: FakeCompletion

Figure 8: RPO, InstructionsOverride

Figure 9: RPO, FakeCompletion

Figure 10: Spotlighting with Delimiting, PrivilegedAuthorityAdvise

Figure 11: Prompt Sandwiching, TrustEscalation

A.2 Control-Plane

Figure 12: Rug-pull - Spotlighting with Delimiting

Figure 13: Tool shadowing - Spotlighting with Delimiting

A.3 Adaptive Optimization

Figure 14: Adaptive optimization

Figure 15: Adaptive optimization, Spotlighting with Delimiting defense.

A.4 Browser Sandbox Evasion Impact

Figure 16: FakeCompletion with sandbox evasion impact

Figure 17: RPO, InstructionsOverride with sandbox evasion impact

Figure 18: RPO with sandbox evasion impact.

Figure 19: VirtualContextScaffolding with sandbox evasion impact.